

Volume 9, Number 2, June, 2024

Geo-Studies Forum

An International Journal of Environmental & Policy Issues

*A Publication of the Department of Geography
and Environmental Management
University of Ilorin*

GEO-STUDIES FORUM

An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

Geo studies is a peer-reviewed journal, published by the Department of Geography and Environmental Management, University of Ilorin, Nigeria. The purpose of the journal is to make quickly available the fruits of Geography related researches with emphasis on the tropical environment. Contributions are therefore invited from any part of the broad field constituted by geographical or spatial sciences and studies in their economic, political, social and policy dimensions. Research may be broadly defined, but must be sound in methodology, critical, entertaining, analytical, make contribution to existing knowledge and conclusions drawn must address contemporary issues.

CALL FOR PAPERS

We cordially request the submission of original papers for possible inclusion in the forthcoming issue of GEO-STUDIES FORUM (ISSN 1596-4116), published by the Department of Geography and Environmental Management, University of Ilorin.

AREAS OF INTEREST

This scholarly peer-reviewed journal accepts original articles covering, but not limited to, the following areas:

- Geography
- Environmental Management
- Climate Science
- Soil Science
- Water Resources Management
- Biogeography
- Indigenous Knowledge System

- Urban and Regional Planning
- Transport Studies
- Demography
- Tourism Studies
- Geographic Information System (GIS)
- Disaster Risk Management

GUIDELINES FOR PAPER SUBMISSION

MANUSCRIPT PREPARATION

- Language: British English
- Format: Microsoft Word (MS)
- Paper Size: A4
- Font: Times New Roman
- Font Size: 12
- Line Spacing: Double
- Page Limit: 20 pages (excluding references)
- Abstract: Not more than 250 words, single-spaced
- Keywords: 4-5

MANUSCRIPT STRUCTURE

- Title
- Authors' names and affiliations (including emails of all authors, with the corresponding author clearly indicated)
- Abstract
- Introduction
- Methodology
- Findings
- Conclusion
- Recommendations

REFERENCES

- Format: APA
- Line Spacing: Single with hanging indent
- Space between references: 12 pt

SUBMISSION

- Submit to:
geostudiesforum@unilorin.edu.ng
- Include evidence of payment of nonrefundable assessment fee of ₦10,000 (Ten thousand Naira only)

PUBLICATION FEE

Upon acceptance, submit the reviewed manuscript with evidence of payment of a non-refundable fee of ₦20,000 (Twenty thousand Naira only)

BANK DETAILS

- **Account Name:** GEOSTUDIES FORUM
- **Account Number:** 2324256060
- **Bank:** UBA

CONTENTS

A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF OPEN SPACES AND THE LOCATION OF MECHANIC WORKSHOPS IN RESIDENTIAL AREAS OF AKURE TOWNSHIP <i>O. B. Akinbamijo, F. K. Omole, and M. K. Alakinde</i>	1 - 16
ANALYSIS OF THE SPATIAL PATTERN OF DIVORCE ACROSS THE SENATORIAL ZONES OF BENUE STATE, NIGERIA <i>Mary Otanwa Ubi, Andrew Egba Ubogu and Olanrewaju Yusuf Yahaya</i>	17 - 35
ANALYSIS OF FLOOD DISASTER RISK AND EXPOSURE IN THE COMMUNITIES OF KIRI DAM'S CATCHMENT, ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA <i>Ikusemoran Mayomi, Mukthar Alhaji, and Sambo Rita</i>	36 - 54
USE OF MOTORCYCLE AS ALTERNATIVE MEANS OF TRANSPORT IN OGBOMOSO, NIGERIA <i>Saka Nurudeen, Raji Abdulquadri Akande, and Taiwo Luqman Adedeji</i>	55 - 68
EXAMINATION OF CO-OPERATORS' SATISFACTION WITH STRATEGIES OF HOUSING FINANCE OF COOPERATIVE SOCIETIES IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN KWARA STATE <i>Abdullahi Taiye Ibrahim, Sakariyau, Jamiu Kayode, Ajibade, Kayode Rasheed, AbdulHafeez, and Sulaiman AbdulKarim</i>	69 - 83
EVALUATION OF LAND USE LAND COVER CHANGES OF KIMBA/RITAWA GRAZING RESERVE IN NORTHEASTERN NIGERIA <i>Abubakar Hassan</i>	84 - 90
LAND SUITABILITY ASSESSMENT FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT USING GIS AND MULTI-CRITERIA EVALUATION APPROACH IN KATSINA METROPOLIS, KATSINA STATE, NIGERIA <i>Yahaya Zayyana Ibrahim and Safiyanu Mohammed</i>	91 - 100
TOWARDS URBAN ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY: MANAGEMENT AND CHALLENGES OF ELECTRONIC WASTE IN MAIDUGURI METROPOLIS, BORNO STATE <i>Kodiya M. A., Abdussalam B., Yusuf F. I., Buba W., and Yusuf A.</i>	101 - 116

EDITORIAL BOARD

- Dr I.O Orire:** orire.io@unilorin.edu.ng
08032942992
- Prof. L.T. Ajibade:** edabijalt@unilprin.edu.ng
08075251963
- Dr B.A. Usman:** usman.ba@unilorin.edu.ng
08036909201
- Dr Toluwalope M. Agaja:** agaja.tm@unilorin.edu.ng
07032329906
- Prof. Roda M. Olanrewaju:** lamoji@unilorin.edu.ng
08057674931
- Prof. Afolabi M. Tunde:** afolabi@unilorin.edu.ng
08038540145

EDITORIAL ADVISORY BOARD

- Prof. Gbadegesin, A. S. -** Dept. of Geography, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.
08033661346
adeniyig55@gmail.com
- Prof. Abdullahi, John -** Dept of Geography, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.
08036821438
drajohn74@gmail.com
- Prof. Ogunbodede, E. Funlayo -** Dept. of Geography & Planning Sciences, Adekunle Ajasin
University, Akungba, Ondo State.
08077860313
emmanuel.ogunbodede@aaua.edu.ng
- Prof. Akoteyon, I. S. -** Dept. of Environmental Management, Lagos State University,
Ojo, Lagos State. 08023161616
isaiah.akoteyon@lasu.edu

PATRON

- Prof. Adedayo, A. F. (Rtd.) -** Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of
Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

JOURNAL'S CONTACTS

Address: Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.

Emails: geostudiesforum@unilorin.edu.ng, edabijalt@unilorin.edu.ng

Website: Visit the journal website at: Geo-Studies Forum

TOWARDS URBAN ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY: MANAGEMENT AND CHALLENGES OF ELECTRONIC WASTE IN MAIDUGURI METROPOLIS, BORNO STATE

¹Kodiya M. A., ²Abdussalam B., ³Yusuf F. I., ⁴Buba W., ⁵Yusuf A.

^{1, 2 & 5}Department of Geography, University of Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria

³Department of Geography, Federal College of Education, Yola Adamawa state Nigeria

⁴Department of Urban & Regional Planning, Federal Polytechnic Kaltungo, Gombe State Nigeria

Corresponding Author's E-mail aminkodiya@unimaid.edu.ng

Abstract: *The study aimed to assess the Management and challenges of electronic waste in Maiduguri Metropolis. The objectives of the study were to identify the types of E-waste owned by the electronic repair technicians, determine the Level of awareness of electronic waste, examine the environmental and health effects of E-waste, and to identify the disposal and management practices employed by the respondents. Questionnaire and interview techniques were used in gathering information from 254 Electronic repair technicians selected through purposive and systematic random sampling techniques. Descriptive statistic was used to analyze the result. The study revealed that electronic repairer is a male dominated occupation with a mean age of 20.5. Scrap mobile phones were the major electronic waste found in the electronic repair technician's workshop as indicated by 55.2%. The Study revealed that majority of the respondents displayed a notable lack of awareness regarding the adverse environmental and health effects of e-waste, knowledge regarding legislation and proper management of the waste. The study also uncovered improper disposal measures for e-waste, as most of the electronic repairers mixed their e-waste with any other solid wastes and dispose to the collection sites or throw them to the surrounding area. Furthermore, majority of e-waste collection and recycling work is done by manually dismantling of the obsolete equipment using primitive tools and methods such as unsafe burning and melting to separate metals, due to absence of recycling facilities. The study recommended that relevant authorities should prioritize raising awareness regarding e-waste management and the existing e-waste legislation that enables proper management practices. In addition, the creation of e-waste collection and recycling centers in the study area will encourage sustainable practices and promote environmentally friendly approaches within the e-waste industry and ultimately contribute to sustainable development in the long term.*

Key words: Challenges, Electronic Waste, Environment, Management, Sustainability

INTRODUCTION

The escalating issue of e-waste, a term for discarded electrical and electronic equipment, continues to exacerbate environmental

degradation. In 2019 alone, the world saw the generation of an alarming 53.6 million tons of such waste (Lynda, Santoso, and Winbowo., 2021). The challenges of managing this waste

is particularly acute in developing nations, where inadequate funding, lack of interest in sustainable solutions, inefficient urban planning, substandard waste collection infrastructure, and burgeoning urban populations converge to create a dire public health and environmental crisis (Petronijevic, Dodevic, Stefanovic, Arsovki, Krevokapic and Mistic. 2020).

Proper end-of-life (EOL) management of these products, which involves either disposal or processing for material and/or energy recovery are crucial. E-waste, often the by-product of electronic goods that have outlived their utility, is proliferating at an unprecedented rate due to consumer appetites for the latest technologies. Kumar and Dixit (2018) observed that rapid technological progress and corporate pressures for increased profitability have led to a cycle of frequent updates to electronic product lines, offering new and more affordable options. This trend has not only reduced the lifespan of electronic goods but also led to their premature disposal, even before they have exhausted their potential utility.

The composition of e-waste is diverse, encompassing a range of valuable materials including both non-precious (iron, steel, copper, aluminum) and precious metals (gold, silver, palladium, platinum), as well as plastics and various hazardous substances such as lead, mercury, cadmium, batteries, flame retardants, chlorofluorocarbons, and other coolants, all of which pose significant environmental threats (Genchi, Sinicropi, Lauria, Carocci and Catalano., 2020).

In Africa, the reliance on imported refurbished electronic appliances from developed nations is a testament to the continent's increased E-

waste in the waste stream. The Global E-waste Monitor 2020 report highlights a concerning trend that Africa recycles a mere 0.9% of its 2.9 million tonnes of electronic waste, but only 13 African nations including Nigeria have enacted national e-waste legislation, policies, or regulations, signaling a significant gap in the continent's e-waste management strategies (Ghimire & Ariya., 2020).

Additional research indicates that e-waste poses significant challenges for urban practitioners in developing countries, as many of them lack modern environmental management infrastructure (Dzah, Agyapong, Apprey, Agbevanu, & Kagbetor. 2022). Developed countries which tend to consume more electronics, generate larger amounts of e-waste. These nations generally have well-established e-waste management systems and specific regulations in place. However, informal waste collectors, often referred to as scavengers, are primarily responsible for sorting and gathering e-waste from city garbage bins and landfills and unfortunately, these scavengers and other informal collectors often dispose of the e-waste in environmentally hazardous ways (Kodiya, Shettima, Modu & Yusuf, 2023).

Proper management also encompasses various practices, including secondary use, controlled recycling, component recovery, and land filling (Kumari, Sharma, Panesar, Chandrawanshi, Yadav, and Jugal, 2021). Presently, a significant portion of e-waste generated in developing nations is handled without regulation by the informal division, which employs harmful techniques such as open burning, unregulated landfill disposal, open dumping, informal dismantling, and artisanal recycling (Nuwematsiko, Oporia, Nabirye, Halage, Musoke and Buregyeya, 2021). Electronic repair technicians and scrap

merchants play better roles in e-waste management. However, Nigeria currently lacks clear plans for e-waste disposal. Unfortunately, e-waste is piling up in electronic technicians' workshops, offices, households and other enterprises across the country due to outdated or malfunctioning equipment, leading to storage and disposal challenges (Kumari *et al.*, 2021).

In Maiduguri, the absence of a formal e-waste management framework exacerbates the problem. Electronic waste is often relegated to open dump or incinerated, practices that emit dangerous pollutants into the environment. These actions not only threaten public health and safety but also overlook the potential for resource recovery and recycling. The informal e-waste recycling sector in Maiduguri is largely driven by scavengers whom without appropriate equipment or protective gear, are at risk of harmful exposure. The health implications for these individuals and their communities are profound and distressing. Research on e-waste generation, management, and its environmental and health impacts in Nigeria and other developing countries is extensive, with significant contributions from scholars such as Miner, Rampedi, Ifegbesan, and Machete (2020); Ben-Enukora, Okorie, Oresanya, Ekanem (2017) and Dzah *et al.*, (2022).

Yet, studies specific to Maiduguri have primarily focused on broader issues of solid Waste Management, effects of indiscriminate waste disposal, the consequences of haphazard disposal, and waste scavenging as noted by Kodiya *et al.* (2023), Umar and Bukar., 2022, Mukhtar and Joseph (2018) and Dauda and Osita (2003). A glaring deficiency remains in the comprehensive assessment of e-waste management practices in Maiduguri. This Study aimed to bridge the identified gaps in

existing literature by providing a detailed examination of the current state of e-waste among electronic repair technicians in this locale.

It became pertinent therefore, to assess the management and challenges of electronic waste in Maiduguri, with the following objectives: identification of the types of e-waste owned by the electronic repair technicians; determination of the level of awareness of electronic waste among the respondents; examination of the environmental and health effects of e-waste; and identification of the disposal and management practices employed by the respondents.

This study is vital as most consumers see the technicians as last resort for consultation when their devices develop problems; especially when the warranty period of their devices have elapsed. Often times, it is the electronic repair technicians that determine when the devices become wastes and what happens to those e-wastes. By doing so, it seeks to inform policy development and the implementation of sustainable e-waste management solutions among electronic repair technicians in Maiduguri, fostering environmental sustainability and public health.

METHODOLOGY

STUDY AREA

Maiduguri, the Borno State Capital is the largest city in the North eastern part of Nigeria. It is located between latitudes 11° 43' N and 11° 52' N and Longitudes 13° 05' E and 13° 15' E. It has a total area of 543km², with an altitude of 345 meters. It is characterized by low precipitation of 650 mm with highest rainfall in August and greater part in the month of July, August and September.

Generally, the mean monthly temperature is always above 20°C. The major economic activities of the people of the city include commerce in primary products mostly agricultural goods, manufactured goods and tertiary services such as banking and transportation. Other small-scale activities are hawkers, small trade and craft stands, open mechanic workshops, vulcanizers, fuel

hawkers, corner shops, kiosks, stalls, gas sales, and several other varieties of goods and services following the mass influx of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Maiduguri Metropolis, arising from the insecurity challenges in many parts of the State.

Figure 1: Map of Maiduguri Metropolis
Source: GIS Lab, Department of Geography, UNIMAID (2024)

The study was a cross sectional survey conducted in Maiduguri the Borno State capital, between July, 2023 and April, 2024. The sampling frame was composed of electronic repair technicians who repair Mobile Phones, faulty ICT devices; radios, televisions, computers, (desktops and laptops)

and printers in Bulumkuttu GSM Market. Purposive and systematic sampling techniques were adopted for this study. Bulumkuttu GSM market was purposively selected due to the high concentration of electronic repair technician workshops in the market. Systematic random sampling technique was

also used to select the respondents for the study.

The market consisted of 710 mobile phone and other accessories repairers who have registered with their trade association (Records of trade association, 2023). 254 respondents were sampled to represent the entire population using the Krejcie and Morgan (1979) table of sample size determination for population proportion of 0.5 and 95% confidence level. Starting point was obtained using a random number table with a sampling interval of 3.

Questionnaire and interview techniques were used in gathering information for the study. The interview was administered to 20 heads of the electronic technician trade association. Informed consent was obtained in writing from all the respondents before the commencement of the study. Respondents who could not write were requested to thumb print in place of their signature. The copies of the questionnaires were administered using two research assistants from the Department of Geography, University of Maiduguri, who are conversant with the local environment. The questionnaire was divided into four parts: the first part dealt with the demographic information of the respondent, the second on e-waste types and components, the third part centered on the awareness of e-waste while the fourth part focused on management and challenges of e-waste.

The questionnaire was pre-tested on 20 Electronic repair technicians outside the sample before the commencement of data collection and later adjustments and corrections were made on some of the items. Data for the study were analyzed using the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 21. Frequency counts and

simple percentages were used and presented in Tables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the result of the investigation into the management and challenges associated with electronic waste in Maiduguri. The study identified several pressing challenges including inadequate infrastructure for e-waste collection and recycling, lack of awareness regarding proper disposal practices, leading to environmental pollution and human health risk.

SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS

The socio-demographic characteristics of the sampled respondents are shown in Table 1. The study revealed that all the respondents were male with age ranged between 20 and 51 years (mean age= 20.5), This implies that women do not participate in an informal e-waste-related businesses in the study area, and this might be due to the possible exposure of women to gender-related harassment, high-energy demand nature of the work and the culture of the study area that restrict women in participating in certain occupation. This finding is in tandem with other studies that revealed male dominance in informal waste related business (Kodiya *et al.*, 2023, Taiwo *et al.*, 2022; Nuhu *et al.*, 2022).

The age statistics in this study showed that electronic repair is one of the few jobs available to youths in Nigeria as a means of poverty alleviation, primarily due to persistent unemployment. Married respondents constituted 62.2% and singles 37.8%. Majority (61%) of the respondents were observed to be literate. The percentages of electronic repair technicians that attained primary, secondary, tertiary and non-formal

education was 18%, 29%, 14% and 39% respectively. This is an indication of the fact

that it is possible for some of the electronic repair technicians to attend school while still engaging in the business.

Table 1: Socio Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variable	Frequency n = 254	Percentage (%)
Age		
<20 years	53	20.9
21-30 years	95	37.4
31-40 years	53	20.9
41-50 years	26	10.2
51 years and above	27	10.6
Total	254	100
Education		
Non formal	99	39
Primary	47	18
Secondary	74	29
Tertiary	36	14
Total	254	100
Marital status		
Single	158	62.2
Married	96	37.8
Total	254	100
Ethnicity		
Kanuri	93	36.6
Hausa	90	35.4
Igbo	21	8.3
Yoruba	31	12.2
Others	19	7.5
Total	254	100

Source: Field Work, 2024

TYPE OF E-WASTE OWNED BY THE RESPONDENTS

The percentages of the different electronic waste owned by the surveyed electronic repair technicians are depicted in table 2. Slightly more than half (55.2%) of the respondents possess scrap mobile phones. As also confirmed by a related study in Nigeria (Okoye and Odoh, 2014), mobile phone is the

most widely used essential electronic device owned by several households due to its large product consumption quantity, continuously decreasing lifespan, and high obsolescence rate as a result of the ongoing advancements and new models launched every year, thereby making this device highly discarded by consumers and adding more to the accumulated e-waste in the waste stream.

According to Nethaji-Mariappan *et al.*, (2017) in a study in India, the purchase of electronic devices can be attributed to income earned and increasing economic growth. However, regardless of the electronic type acquire, these devices at some point reach the end of their

lifespan, thereby requiring disposal. Other devices such as laptops (21.3%), wireless radio/media players (18.5%), Television (2.3%), and other (2.7) e-waste components such as Video Cameras, Audio amplifiers, printers etc. were reported by the respondents.

Table 2: Type of E-Waste Owned by the Respondents

Variable	Frequency n = 254	Percentage (%)
Scrap Mobile Phone	140	55.2
Laptop/Desktop	54	21.3
Wireless, Radio, Mp3	47	18.5
Television Set	6	2.3
Others	7	2.7
Total	254	100

Source: Field Work, 2024

E-WASTE COMPONENTS RECOVERED BY THE RESPONDENTS

Electronic devices composed of plastics, glasses, battery and other precious metals. Over 1,000 materials are used to manufacture electronic devices (Transel, 2017). Maphosa and Maphosa (2020) highlights that the manufacture of electronic devices is a complex process with over thousand substances, including rare earth metals such as palladium, gold, copper and platinum, are mixed with toxic substances such as arsenic, mercury, cadmium and lead and many more. Technological obsolescence of electronic products leads to an increase in the amount of E-Waste generated in the environment. It is also becoming easier and more convenient to change malfunctioning equipment than to

repair or fix them while electronic products may contain reusable and valuable materials (Lukmon *et al.*, 2023). Most of the components in E-Waste are however hazardous and toxic, hence unsafe to the environment. Data on the E-waste component recovered by the respondents as shown on table 3 revealed that circuit boards account for the 38.6% of the recovered components. This was followed by copper (23.2%), battery (22.2%), Plastic (9%) and metals and aluminum (7%). These findings indicate that a significant number of respondents prioritize the recovery of circuit boards. This contradicts the findings of Okoye and Odoh (2014) that identified plastic as the most commonly recovered components in their study.

Table 3: E-waste Components Recovered by the Respondents

Variable	Frequency n = 254	Percentage (%)
Circuit board	98	38.6
Plastic	23	9
Battery Components	56	22.2
Copper	59	23.2
Metal and Aluminum	18	7
Total	254	100

Source: Field Work, 2024

LEVEL OF AWARENESS OF ELECTRONIC WASTE

Awareness variables were measured on a five points Likert scale with possible responses including strongly agree, agree, strongly disagree, disagree and undecided. E-waste awareness was summed to create the scale of measurement on a 95-point scale so that a score of >70% indicates high awareness, 50-70% indicates moderate awareness and <50% indicates low awareness respectively. As shown on table 4, the study revealed that majority (77%) of the Participants possessed high knowledge regarding the presence of electronic waste. This is in agreement with a related study in Ghana (Dzah *et al.*, 2022), Nigeria (Miner *et al.*, 2020) and Australia (Islam *et al.*, 2021), where respondents under study are aware of e-waste.

About 70.9% of the studied groups are having low awareness of the existing e-waste regulations. Similar results were observed in other studies (Dzah *et al.*, 2022; Nuwematsiko *et al.*, 2021). The National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) is the main agency handling environmental regulations in Nigeria.

There are various acts with penalties as high as imprisonment and fines. These environmental acts guiding waste include the Harmful Waste (Special Criminal Provisions) Act, Cap. HI, 2004, the National Environmental (Sanitation and Waste Control) Regulation 2009 and the Environmental Impact Assessment Act, Cap E1.

In spite of these regulations, the reported low awareness of the existing E-waste regulation in this study could possibly have resulted from inadequate enforcement of existing legislation, lack of coordination between various agencies and the public in comprehending e-waste regulation, lack of public awareness on the inherent dangers of handling E-Waste as it is regarded as a business opportunity, absence of E-Waste recycling facilities, and there is poor (if any) corporate social responsibility on the part of industries on E-Waste. Enhancing awareness of e-waste regulations can play a crucial role in promoting responsible practices for e-waste management and mitigating the adverse consequences associated with improper handling.

Despite the global recognition of the detrimental effects of e-waste, majority

(71.7%) of the respondents displayed a notable lack of awareness regarding the adverse environmental and health effects associated with e-waste (Table 4). What is disturbing is the fact that some of these educated electronic repair technicians are well experienced in the trade area for many years, but they do not consider it a serious problem. Most of the repairers are after the economic benefits accrued from e-waste repairing while the environmental and health hazards are blatantly disregarded. Similar results were obtained in previous studies (Ali and Akalu., 2022; Kitila and Woldemikael 2021; Abebe *et al.*, 2017; Ohajinwa., 2017) indicating that

majority of the studied subject lack awareness of environmental and health risks associated with e-waste. Compared with studies in other part of the world, awareness about the environmental and health effects of E-waste is extremely low (Nuwematsiko *et al.*, 2021; Azodo *et al.*, 2017). Two third (68.1%) of the respondents have low Awareness of toxic hazardous substances in E-Waste. The proportion is slightly lower than the observed 92. 4% in Ethiopia (Ali and Akalu., 2022). It is important to note that e-waste contains toxic substances which can pose risks to human health and the environment if not properly managed. E-waste consists of many different substances, including toxic materials and heavy metals, as well as organic pollutants.

Table 4: Level of awareness of electronic waste

	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Awareness of Existence of Electronic waste	High	196	77
	Moderate	30	12
	Low	28	11
Awareness of Environmental and Health Risk associated with E-waste	High	12	4.7
	Moderate	60	23.6
	Low	182	71.7
Awareness of Existing Laws on E-waste Disposal and Management	High	9	3.5
	Moderate	65	25.6
	Low	180	70.9
Awareness of toxic hazardous substances in E-Waste	High	14	5.5
	Moderate	67	26.4
	Low	173	68.1

Source: Field Work, 2024

ENVIRONMENTAL AND HEALTH EFFECTS OF E-WASTE

With respect to Environmental and health effects of e-waste, data on table 5 revealed that 60.2% of the electronic repair technicians identified soil contamination as the major environmental effects of unsustainable e-waste management. It is discovered that e-Waste leaches the soil due to the presence of mercury, cadmium, lead and phosphorus in it. E-Waste can also cause uncontrolled fire risk, leading to toxic fumes. In addition, uncontrolled burning, disassembly and disposal of e-Waste can cause a variety of environmental problems such as groundwater contamination, atmospheric pollution, and occupational health and safety effects among those directly or indirectly involved in the processing of E-Waste (Adanu *et al.*, 2020).

Results of samples taken from water and sediments in Ghana reported that contaminants related to e-waste have made their way into waterways which significantly pollute water bodies by e-waste (Huang., 2014). Also, burning e-waste inappropriately creates a lot of pollution in the air, which can lead to secondary exposure because pollution can travel long distances from recycling sites to other populated regions (Attia *et al.*, 2021).

Apart from soil contamination and Air pollution, Health problems arising from the use of unsustainable e-waste management was reported by 15.8% of the technicians. E-waste contains heavy metals which when exposed lead to various adverse effects in human. Long term or excessive exposure to manganese and zinc compound can cause Parkinson's-like disease and other neurological effects. Furthermore, exposures to metal oxides are also leading to other health issues including serious respiratory problems and reproductive effects (Genchi *et al.*, 2020).

In Malaysia for instance, E-waste and other metal bearing wastes were classified as scheduled waste and required management according to the specified regulations in Environmental Quality (Scheduled Wastes) Regulations 2005 (Noor *et al.*, 2019). 13% of respondents also perceived air pollution as one of the environmental effects of E-waste. The study further revealed that artisans suffered physical injuries while repairing electronic appliances such as body cuts when cutting metals or stepping on metal chippings or pieces of metals lying on the ground, as reported by 11% of the respondents. Other forms of injuries associated with the use of bear hands to dismantle e-waste occurs when hitting materials against each other to break them up or when stones and hammers are used to separate joined metals.

Table 5: Environmental and Health Effects of E-waste

Variable	Frequency n = 254	Percentage (%)
Air Pollution	33	13
Soil Contamination	153	60.2
Health Problems	40	15.8
Physical Injuries	28	11
Total	254	100

Source: Field Work, 2024

DISPOSAL AND MANAGEMENT OF E-WASTE EMPLOYED BY THE RESPONDENTS

Generally, Majority of the electronic repair technicians in this study lack knowledge regarding the proper disposal measures for e-waste. The absence of a comprehensive e-waste management system leads to a situation where many of the e-waste repairers’ resort to burning of e-waste (21.7%), selling the e-waste to scavengers (9.8%), repair or re-use valuable parts of non-functioning devices (27.6%), storing it (11.8%), or even un safe dumping of E-waste (29%) as an alternative solution (Table 6). Similar findings were reported in a related studies (Ali and Akalu., 2022; Nuwematsiko *et al.*, 2021; Miner *et al.*, 2020). Electronic repairers mixed their electronic waste with any other solid wastes and dispose to the collection site or throw to the surrounding area, which may or may not be taken by street sweepers.

This reflects the actual solid waste management practices among the artisans. It has been observed during the study that none of the respondents have separate waste containers for solid waste segregation, which

shows that the E-waste goes to the dumpsites with other waste, instead of being properly recycled. One effective solution is the implementation of curbsides recycling bins special for discarding smaller electronic devices such as mobile phones and their accessories next to general waste bins in the GSM market. This will further encourage the Artisans to dispose off their electronic waste into the right bin instead of throwing them with general waste. Similar finding was obtained in Addis Ababa (Jadhav., 2013). The present study also found that a large portion of e-waste was kept in the electronic repair technicians’s shop probably with the hope for future use of some parts.

Other Respondents revealed in an interview that some desktop computers, Mobile phones and other Electronics in their shops/store room belonged to clients who failed to claim them after being notified that they were beyond repair. Storing e-waste is very common among e-waste repairers, sellers, households and institutions as also confirmed by other studies (Ali and Akalu., 2022; Attia *et al.*, 2021; Borthakur., 2020; Abede., 2017; Ogunsola and Shobajo., 2017). The result of the interview also showed that some of the electronic repair

technicians reuse parts of faulty devices if they are compatible with the new one, and sell the non-compatible ones to waste scavengers. Therefore, re-use will in the long term not

solve the e-waste problem as the obsolete product will eventually be disposed of and most of the e-waste products re-use has a short life span.

Table 6: Disposal and management of E-waste employed by the Respondents

Variable	Frequency n = 254	Percentage (%)
Repair or Re-use valuable parts of non-functioning devices	70	27.6
Storing in the workshop	30	11.8
Selling e-waste to scavengers	25	9.8
Dumpinge-waste in general waste bin	74	29.1
Burning e-waste	55	21.7
Total	254	100

Source: Field Work, 2024

CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH E-WASTE MANAGEMENT

The study revealed that majority (31.5%) of the electronic repair technicians are of the view that capital to acquire new technology is a major challenge to the use of sustainable technologies to retrieve valuable elements from electronic waste (Table 7). Similar study (Adamu *et al.*, 2020) has confirmed that lack of fund was a Major challenge for sustainable E-waste management. The simple reason for this is perhaps the fact that the income earned from repair of electronic devices and sell of e waste is only enough to cater for themselves and families. A few of the respondents (12%) explained further that, absence of recycling facilities is a challenge in managing electronic waste by the artisans. The majority of e-waste collection and recycling work is done locally

in the informal sector through identifying components that can be recover or reused and manually dismantling the obsolete equipment using primitive tools and methods such as burning and melting to separate metals.

Appropriate recycling of e-waste has an economic value as because valuable materials are recovered and used as a source for secondary material supply as well as for reuse in new devices, which in turn help in minimizing the consumption and excessive use of primary raw materials and improve circular economy. Other artisans consider inadequate support from government (7.4%) hinders them to acquire better tools for their work and effective E-waste management.it is essential that government should regulate and formalize the activities of e-waste and artisans and other stakeholders in the waste

management sectors, through providing training and education for workers, and implement safe and environmentally sound processing methods. This will help to protect workers' health, reduce environmental pollution, and ensure the sustainable management of e-waste. This approach not only promotes economic benefits but also contributes to the overall well-being of artisans, communities and other stake holders in the waste stream.

As also shown on table 7, a fraction (17.7%) of the respondents revealed lack of awareness of effective and sustainable e-waste management as a challenge for the electronic

technicians. This finding is in tandem with what obtained in earlier study (Sengupta *et al.*, 2022) but contrast with a similar study (Nuwematsiko *et al.*, 2021) where lack of awareness was not a challenge for e-waste management. The promotion of environmental education is necessary for raising e-waste awareness among young artisans, thereby increasing e-waste recycling. A study by (Dhir., 2021) has shown that awareness about laptops usage and disposal in Japan had a positive impact on laptops disposal practices and increased their recycling rates. Similarly, the absence of collection centers and low patronage are some of the significant challenges identified by artisans.

Table 7: Challenges Associated with E-waste Management

Variable	Frequency n = 254	Percentage (%)
Lack of awareness	45	17.7
Absence of recycling facilities	30	12
Low Patronage	34	13.3
Absence of storage Space	46	18.1
Lack of Fund	80	31.5
Inadequate Government Support	19	7.4
Total	254	100

Source: Field Work, 2024

CONCLUSION

The study has uncovered that despite the global recognition of the detrimental effects of e-waste, majority of the artisans in the study displayed a notable lack of awareness regarding the adverse environmental and health effects associated with e-waste,

knowledge regarding legislation and proper management of e-waste. What is worrisome is the fact that most of the electronic repair technicians are after the economic benefits accrued from e-waste repairing and sells, while the environmental and health hazards are blatantly disregarded. Also, the absence of

a comprehensive e-waste management system in the study area leads to a situation where many of the e-waste repairers' resort to burning of e-waste, selling the e-waste to scavengers, or even unsafe dumping of E-waste as an alternative solution.

Addressing this issue will require authorities to prioritize raising awareness regarding E-waste management and the existing e-waste legislation that enables proper management practices. In addition, the creation of e-waste collection and recycling centers in the study area will encourage sustainable practices and promote environmentally friendly approaches within the e-waste industry and ultimately contribute to sustainable development in the long term. The research covers electronic waste technicians in Bulumkutu GSM Market only. Nevertheless, future studies could expand their investigations to encompass other areas in Maiduguri so as to identify further gaps within the e-waste management system and contribute to developing a comprehensive e-waste inventory for improved sustainable e-waste management in the study area.

REFERENCES

Umar, I.A., & Bukar, M.A. (2022). Solid waste management in Peri-Urban Center of Maiduguri Metropolis. Case Study of Jiddari Polo, Jere Local Government Area of Borno State. *IOSR Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology (IOSR-JESTFT)*, 16(10), 01-05.

Abebe, M.A. (2017). Electronic waste management practices and development of electronic waste Management guidelines in Addis Ababa. *International Journal of Engineering Science*. 2017. 19-18.

Adanu, S.K., Gbedemah, S. F., and Attah, M. K. (2020). Challenges of adopting sustainable

technologies in e-waste management at Agbogbloshie, Ghana. *Heliyon* 6 (2020) e04548

Ali, A. S., & Akalu, Z. K. (2022). E-waste awareness and management among people engaged in e-waste selling, collecting, dismantling, repairing, and storing activities in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *Environmental health insights*, 16, 117863022211191. DOI:10.1177/11786302221119145.

Attia, Y., Soori, P. K., & Ghaith, F. (2021). Analysis of households' e-waste awareness, disposal behavior, and estimation of potential waste mobile phones towards an effective e-waste management system in Dubai. *Toxics*, 9(10), 236. DOI:10.3390/TOXICS9100236

Azodo, A.P., Ogban P.U., and Okpor J. (2021) Knowledge and awareness implication on E-waste management among Nigerian collegiate. *Journal of Applied Science and Environmental Management*. 2017; 21: 1035-1040

Ben-Enukora, C., Okorie, N., Oresanya, T., and Ekanem, T. (2017). Awareness and perception of media campaign on e-waste among residents of Ado-Ota, Nigeria. *Covenant Journal of Communication*. 17 (4) 18–32.

Borthakur, A., & Singh, P. (2020). The Journey from products to waste: A pilot study on perception and discarding of electronic waste in contemporary urban India. *Environment Science Pollution Research*. 28, 24511–24520.

Dauda and Osita (2003). Solid Waste management and re-use in Maiduguri, Nigeria. 29th WEDC International Conference towards MDG, Abuja Nigeria, 2003.

Dhir, A., Malodia, S., Awan, U., Sakashita, M., & Kaur, P. (2021). Extended valence theory perspective on consumers' e-waste recycling intentions in Japan. *Journal of Clean Production*.312, 127443.

Dzah, C., Agyapong, J. O., Apprey, M. W., Agbevanu, K. T., & Kagbetor, P. K. (2022). Assessment of perceptions and practices of electronic waste management among commercial consumers in Ho, Ghana. *Sustainable environment*, 8(1), 1–16. DOI:10.1080/27658511.2022.2048465

Genchi, G., Sinicropi, M.S, Lauria .G.,Carocci. A., Catalano A. (2020). The Effects of Cadmium Toxicity. *Rev. International journal of environmental research and public health*. 17, 37837.

Ghimire, H. &Ariya, P. (2020). E-Wastes: Bridging the Knowledge Gaps in Global Production Budgets, Composition, Recycling and Sustainability Implications. *Sustainable Chemistry*. (1). 154-182. 10.3390/suschem1020012.

Huang, J., Nkrumah, P. N., Anim, D. O., & Mensah, E. (2014). E-waste disposal effects on the aquatic environment: Accra, Ghana. *Reviews of environmental contamination and toxicology*, 229, 19–34. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-03777-62

Islam, M. T., Dias, P., & Huda, N. (2021). Young Consumers e-waste awareness, consumption, disposal, and recycling behavior: A case study of university students in Sydney, Australia. *Journal of cleaner production*, 282, 124490. DOI:10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124490

Jadhav, S. (2013). Electronic waste: a growing concern in today's environment sustainability. *Int J SocSciInterdiscip Res*. 2013, 2:139-147

Kitila, A. W., Woldemikael, S. M. (2021). Electronic waste management in Addis Ababa: the case of bole and Nefas Silk Lafto sub-cities. *African Journal of Science Technology Innovation Development*. 2021; Vol 13:235 246.

Kodiya, M. A, Shettima, M., Modu, M. A., & Yusuf, F. (2023). The Socio-Economic and environmental benefits of waste scavenging in Maiduguri, Borno State. *International Journal of Science for Global Sustainability*, 9(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.57233/ijsgs.v9i1.408>

Kumari, S., Sharma, P., Panesar, S., Chandrawanshi, L., Yadav, G., &Jugal, K. (2021). Exploring the awareness regarding e-waste and its management among electronic repair workers and scrap dealers of South Delhi, India. *Indian journal of occupational and environmental medicine*, 25(3), 178. DOI:10.4103/ijoem.IJOEM_48_19

Kumar, A. and Dixit G. (2018). An analysis of the barriers affecting the implementation of E-waste Management practices in India: A novel ISM-DEMATEL Approach. *Sustainable Production* 14 (18) 36-52 DOI: 10: 1016 JSPC. 2018.01.002.

Lynda, A., Santoso and Winbowo (2021). An assessment of e-waste generation and environmental management of selected countries in Africa, Europe and North America: A systematic review. *Science of the total environment*, 729 (21) 148078

Maphosa, V. &Maphosa, M. (2020). E-waste management in Sub-Saharan Africa: A systematic literature review. *Cogent Business & Management*. 7. 10.1080/23311975.2020.1814503.

Miner, K. J., Rampedi, I. T., Ifegbesan, A. P., & Machete, F. (2020). Survey on household awareness and willingness to participate in e-waste management in jos, plateau state, Nigeria. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(3). DOI:10.3390/su12031047

Mukhtar, A. & Akan, J.C. (2018). Assessment of Challenges facing Solid Waste Management in Maisandari Neighbourhood of Maiduguri Metropolis, Borno State Nigeria. *IJRISS* vol II, Issue VII 18/ ISSN 2454-6186.

Nethaji-Mariappan, V. E., Karthik, S., Vineeth, K. S., Varthamanan, S. (2017). E-waste management and assessment—A review. *International Journal Chem. Tech. Res.* **2017**, 10, 924–936.

Noor, A. H., Yusof, M.Z., and Nor, F. M. (2019). An Overview of Scheduled Wastes Management in Malaysia. *Journal of Wastes and Biomass Management*, 1(2): 01-04.

Nuhu, A., Danbaba, A. A., Jamila G. A. (2022). Analysis of Socio-economic benefits of solid wastes scavenging in Rigasa, Kaduna Metropolis Nigeria. *International Journal of Science for global sustainability*. Vol. 8 (2) pp 47-59

Nuwematsiko, R., Oporia, F., Nabirye, J., Halage, A. A., Musoke, D., & Buregyeya, E. (2021). Knowledge, perceptions, and practices of electronic waste management among consumers in Kampala, Uganda. *Journal of Environment and Public Health*, 2021, 1–11. doi:10.1155/2021/3846428

Ogunsola, k., and Shobajo J.A. (2017). Determinants of Electronic Waste Management Practices among Information and Communication Technology Artisans in Ibadan, Nigeria. *AJSD* Vol. 7 Num 1, 2017

Ohajinwa, C. M., Van Bodegom, P. M., Vijver, M. G., & Peijnenburg, W. J. G. M. (2017). Health risks awareness of electronic waste workers in the informal sector in Nigeria. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 14(8). DOI:10.3390/IJERPH14080911

Okoye, A., and Odoh, C. (2014). Assessment of the Level of Awareness of E-Waste Management and Concern for the Environment amongst the Populace in Onitsha, Southeastern Nigeria. *Journal of Environmental Protection*, 5, 120-134.

Petronijevic, V., Dodevic, A., Stefanovic M., Arsovki, S., Krevokapic, Z and Misic, M. (2020). Energy recovery through end of life vehicle recycling in developing countries. *Sustainability*, 12 (21), 8764 <http://doi.org/10.3390/su12218764>.

Sengupta, D., Ilankoon, I., Kang, K. D., Chong, M. N. (2022). Circular economy and household e-waste management in India: Integration of formal and informal sectors. *Miner. Eng.* 184, 107661. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mineng.2022.107661>.

Taiwo, A. O., Dada, O. T., Ayoola, A. S and Faniran, G. B. (2022). Socio economic, health and environmental aspect of child waste picking activity at Africans largest dump site. *American Journal of Environmental Sciences* 18 (3): 69-80 DOI: 10.3844/ajessp.2022.69.80